

Synthesis of Substituted Benzo[*e,f*]-*s*-indaceno[2,3-*d*]pyrazoles

(MRS) SHARDA KUMARI¹, VIJENDER K GOEL and MEENU MEHTA

Department of Chemistry, M D University, Rohtak-124 001

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Literature survey reveals that scanty attention has been given to heterocycles fused on to indaceno ring. In view of the facile synthesis of benzo[*e,f*]-*s*-indacenone, it was thought worthwhile to fuse pyrazole moiety onto *s*-indaceno ring.

Acenaphthene was reacted with cinnamic acid in the presence of PPA to give a carbonyl compound free from acid. Its ir spectrum exhibited a carbonyl stretching band at 1 680 cm⁻¹ thereby suggesting it to be an α,β -unsaturated six-membered cyclic ketone (2) (Scheme 1). There is a possibility of two angular carbonyl compounds 2b and 2c having five-membered cyclic ketone and it is probably due to crowding near the carbonyl group that the abnormal carbonyl stretching band is being observed. Out of the two possible structures 2b and 2c, the product was assigned the structure 2c in analogy¹ to the reaction of acenaphthene wherein acylation at the position-5 followed by cyclization leads to compound 2c. The structure 2c was further corroborated by the observation of Martin and Greet-Evrard². Finally, the structure 2b was eliminated and 2c was confirmed on the basis of pmr spectrum of the product.

The ketone (2c) was formylated by treatment with ethyl formate in the presence of sodium ethoxide and the result-

ing 8-formyl-7-phenyl-4,5,7,8-tetrahydro-9*H*-benzo[*e,f*]-*s*-indaceno-9-one (3) was reacted with hydrazine hydrate, phenyl hydrazine, semicarbazide hydrochloride and thiosemicarbazide to afford 6,7-dihydro-4-phenyl-1*H*,4*H*-benzo[*e,f*]-*s*-indaceno[2,3-*d*]pyrazole (4), 6,7-dihydro-1,4-diphenyl-1*H*,4*H*-benzo[*e,f*]-*s*-indaceno[2,1-*d*]pyrazole (5), 1-carbamido-6,7-dihydro-4-phenyl-1*H*,4*H*-benzo[*e,f*]-*s*-indaceno-[2,3-*d*]pyrazole (6) and 6,7-dihydro-4-phenyl-1*H*,4*H*-1-thiocarbamidobenzo[*e,f*]-*s*-indaceno[2,3-*d*]pyrazole (7) respectively.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were run on a Beckman IR 4220 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

7-Phenyl-4,5,7,8-tetrahydro-9*H*-benzo[*e,f*]-*s*-indaceno-9-one (2) : Acenaphthene (1 : 10.0 g, 0.065 mol) was condensed with cinnamic acid (9.77 g, 0.066 mol) in the presence of PPA at 60–70° with stirring for 2 h and then cooled. It was poured into water and neutralised with sodium bicarbonate solution. The separated solid was washed with water and crystallised from methanol, (12.03 g, 65.3%), m.p. 140–41°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 8.52 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 2.5 Hz, H-1), 7.52–7.30 (7H, m, H-2, H-3 and C-C₆H₅), 7.25 (1H, s, H-6), 3.42 (4H, s, C-4 and C-5 methylene), 3.39 (1H, t, H-7) and 3.02 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, C-8 methylene).

8-Formyl-7-phenyl-4,5,7,8-tetrahydro-9*H*-benzo[*e,f*]-*s*-indaceno-9-one (3) : The ketone (2; 1.7 g, 0.006 mol) was treated with freshly distilled ethyl formate (0.56 g, 0.0075 mol) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (prepared by reacting 1.5 g sodium metal with 5 ml ethanol). The mixture was shaken vigorously for 4 h at 0° and allowed to stand for 12 h. The contents were then poured into water and the unreacted ketone was extracted with solvent ether. The aqueous layer was acidified and the formyl derivative was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform layer was washed with water, dried over Na₂SO₄ and solvent stripped off to afford crude product (0.93 g, 50%) which was used as such for subsequent steps.

6,7-Dihydro-4-phenyl-1*H*,4*H*-benzo[*e,f*]-*s*-indaceno-[2,3-*d*]pyrazole (4) : Formyl ketone (3; 0.624 g, 0.002 mol) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (5 ml) in ethanol (30 ml) for 7 h. The contents were then cooled and poured into water. The solid separated was washed with water, dried and crystallised from petroleum ether (0.28 g, 46.2%), m.p.

Scheme 1 Reagents (i) C₆H₅CH=CHCOOH/PPA, (ii) HCOOC₂H₅/C₂H₅ONa and (iii) NH₂NHR

NOTE

165–66° (Found : C, 85.9; H, 5.0; N, 9.3, $C_{22}H_{16}N_2$ requires : C, 85.71; H, 5.19; N, 9.09%); δ (DMSO- d_6) 9.48 (1H, s, NH), 7.84 (1H, dd, J 9.0, 2.5 Hz, H-10), 7.40 (1H, s, H-3), 7.70–7.27 (8H, m, H-5, H-8, H-9 and C- C_6H_5), 3.88 (1H, s, H-4) and 2.50 (4H, s, C-6 and C-7 methylene).

6,7-Dihydro-1,4-diphenyl-1H,4H-benzo[e,f]-s-indaceno[2,3-d]pyrazole (5) : Formyl ketone (3); 0.624 g, 0.002 mol) was refluxed with phenyl hydrazine (0.28 g, 0.0026 mol) in glacial acetic acid for 3 h. Usual work up and crystallisation with petroleum ether yielded the product (0.30 g, 40.1%). m.p. 88–90° (Found : C, 87.7; H, 5.4; N, 7.61, $C_{28}H_{20}N_2$ requires : C, 87.50; H, 5.21; N, 7.29%); δ ($CDCl_3$), 7.80 (1H, dd, J 9.0, 2.5 Hz, H-10), 7.44 (1H, t, H-9), 7.30 (1H, s, H-5), 7.22 (1H, s, H-3), 7.54–6.72 (11H, m, C- C_6H_5 , N- C_6H_5 and H-8), 3.36 (1H, s, H-4) and 2.10 (4H, s, C-6 and C-7 methylene).

1-Carbamido-6,7-dihydro-4-phenyl-1H,4H-benzo[e,f]-s-indaceno[2,3-d]pyrazole (6) : Formyl ketone (3); 0.62 g, 0.002 mol) was refluxed with semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.195 g, 0.0026 mol) in glacial acetic acid for 8 h. Usual work up and recrystallisation with benzene petroleum ether (3 : 7) afforded the product (0.33 g, 46.5%), m.p. 223–24° (Found : C, 78.8; H, 4.9; N, 12.2. $C_{23}H_{17}N_3O$ requires : C, 78.63; H, 4.84; N, 11.97%); δ ($CDCl_3$ + DMSO- d_6), 8.38 (1H, dd, J 9.0, 2.5 Hz, H-10), 7.70 (1H, s, H-5), 7.55 (1H,

s, H-3), 7.66–7.27 (7H, m, H-8, H-9 and C- C_6H_5), 5.09 (1H, s, H-4), 3.46 (2H, bs, NH_2) and 3.20 (1H, s, C-6 and C-7 methylene).

6,7-Dihydro-4-phenyl-1H,4H-1-thiacarbamidobenzo[e,f]-s-indaceno[2,3-d]pyrazole (7) : Formyl ketone (3); 0.624 g, 0.002 mol) was treated with thiosemicarbazide (0.236 g, 0.0026 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) for 8 h. Usual work up and crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (4 : 6) yielded the product (0.31 g, 42.3%), m.p. 157–58° (Found : C, 75.4; H, 4.4; N, 11.6. $C_{23}H_{17}N_3S$ requires : C, 75.20; H, 4.63; N, 11.44%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 8.35 (1H, dd, J 9.0 2.5 Hz, H-10) 7.65 (1H, s, H-5), 7.50 (1H, s, H-3), 7.60–7.15 (7H, m, H-8, H-9 and C- C_6H_5), 5.04 (1H, s, H-4), 3.12 (4H, s, C-6 and C-7 methylene) and 2.30 (2H, bs, NH_2).

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